

An Assessment of Availability of Household Amenities and Ownership in Uttarakhand

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ABSTRACT

Performance of any country is not just its economic development but also its social development. Quality of life or well-being is a multidimensional approach and leads to social development in narrow sense and sustainable economic development in broader sense. Quality of life is a subjective measure uses subjective happiness indices by asking people about the living conditions, life satisfaction, happiness and pain and assessing it subjectively. It is helpful in measuring Human Development Index, Index of Well Being, Gross Happiness Index. The standard of living of a person is not determined only by himself or according to his own whims and desires. He has also to consider what society expects from him. There are number of factors on which the quality of life or living condition of an individual depends such as income, size of the family, education, taste and temperament, social customs, general price level, family support like financing of education, housing facilities, structure of family or households structure also plays a significant role in determining one's living standard as many studies from the past reveal. Well-being of a person depends on the availability of basic household amenities and assets which are essential for making day to day activities easier and to maintain the quality of life of an individual or households.

In this paper, well-being in Uttarakhand is evaluated by assessing the changing scenario in quality of life or living conditions of households using 17 indicators based on the availability of households amenities and households assets in rural and urban areas of Uttarakhand between year 2001 and year 2011.

Keywords: Well-being, Quality of life, Standard of living, Economic Development, Social development, Housing amenities

JEL Classification Codes: I3, O1

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I. INTRODUCTION

"I do not want India to be an economic power, I want India to be a happy country."

- J.R.D Tata

Performance of any country is not just its economic development but also its social development. Well-being is the degree to which an individual enjoy a healthy and comfortable life. Well-being of a person or country depends on the availability of basic household amenities and assets which are essential for making our day to day activities easier and to maintain the life quality of an individual or households. Well-being should be studied as the process that includes material, relational and subjective dimensions. Well-being is assessed at the individual level and at the collective level (collectively for the world, nation, state or group of individuals). A group effort to enhance well-being is best as all individuals will automatically have a good standard of living (Sarah, 2010). The concept of quality of life is ambiguous as it can refer to both individual experiences of his or her own life and to the living condition of the people of a country. Quality of life is a subjective measure as a person can define the quality of life on the basis of wealth and satisfaction from life while another person can define the quality of life in terms of capabilities. A disabled person may report a high quality of life, whereas a healthy person who recently lost a job may report a low quality of life.

The standard of living of a person is not determined only by himself or according to his own whims and desires. He has also to consider what society expects from him. There are number of factors on which the quality of life or living condition of an individual depends such as income, size of the family, education, taste and temperament, social custom and conventions and general price level etc. Four important factors are included for the examination of human well-being i.e. Education, health, living condition and economic situation (Zia, 2013). Evaluating well-being involves the use of alternative approaches such as: the very first approach used in the measurement of well-being is adjusted GDP. The second approach to the measurement of well-being is dashboard indicators: this approach combines the unrelated indicators of well-being and presents them as a single indicator. The third approach is composite indices: this approach gives importance to GDP as well as other aspects of well-being like education health etc., for example, Human Development Index, Canadian Index of Well Being, Gross Happiness Index (Bhutan). Fourth one is Subjective happiness indices: it measures well-being by asking people about the satisfaction from life and assessing it subjectively. There is no perfect approach to measure well-being but adjusted GDP approach is widely used and accepted (Hawkins, n.d.). Family support, like, financing of education and housing facilities have a great impact on individual's standard of living. Structure of family or household structure also plays a significant role in determining one's living standard as many studies from the past have revealed that the families headed by females have a low living standard as compared to the male-headed family. The living condition of the family largely depends on social and demographic factors like education, age, place of residence etc. Families with the youngest heads (age 14-24) are poor and have the bad living condition. There is need for right policies by the government to solve the problem of poverty in female-headed houses and identify the factors like age, education etc which are the basic causes of poverty (Mberu, 2007).

Based on the density of population, development, amenities, employment opportunities, education, etc. human settlement is majorly divided into two categories i.e. Urban and Rural. Urban refers to a human settlement where the rate of urbanization and industrialization is high. On the other hand, in a rural settlement, is one where the rate of urbanization is quite slow.

The gap between the Scale of living and Standard of living is an important factor for Economic Growth. Scale of living is defined as the current level of living or current standard of living of an individual or family. It consists of the total wealth they consume, plus the amount of leisure time and how it is utilized. Scale also includes number of family members and their contribution to family income. The future goals or objective of individuals and family is defined as the standard of living (Tuttle, 1960). Objective and subjective quality of life are defined as the two dimensions of quality of life. Objective quality of life shows the external condition of life which includes the physical environment, economic and technical factor. Subjective quality of life focuses on well-being of an individual and includes psychological factors like health, job satisfaction, happiness etc. (Das, 2008).

Standard of living is measured on the basis of gross domestic product (GDP) but GDP is not the only indicator of standard of living. The standard of living also includes health, environment, leisure, etc. which is not measured under GDP. Government policies should focus on increase in GDP through reducing the rate of inflation, reducing biases in the tax system, policies to improve education and investments in research and development program to promote innovation which in turn will help to maintain a higher standard of living (Fledstein, 1997). The earlier standard of living of people was the reflection of the economic growth and accumulated wealth but with time standard of living has included other factors like health, education, housing, and equality (Browning, n.d.). One of the main measures of standard of living also includes health. A height of the individual is generally considered to be dependent on genetic factors but this research highlights that stature shows a lot about the person's health and standard of living as it measures the inequality in the form of nutritional deprivation (Steckel, 1995).

While macro environment is important, microenvironment also plays a prominent role in defining quality of life. Basic amenities like access to electricity, water and sanitation, various public goods do have a lot of importance. In face many such small but important amenities play important role both in terms of directly improving the quality of life and also through its role as an enhancer variable for other factors improving the overall standard of living (Mohanty, 2014). Studies have observed that access to improved sanitation facilities has a critical role in controlling malnutrition and disease-mortality incidences (Mohanty, 2016).

II. OBJECTIVES

The main aim of the study to assess the changing scenario in quality of life through living conditions of households in rural and urban areas of Uttarakhand between year 2001 and year 2011, to evaluate government initiatives for improving the quality of life and to give policy suggestions.

III. DATA AND METHODS

Secondary data is used from different sources such as Census 2001 and Census 2011. Data gathered was analyzed using methods of descriptive analysis.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Well-being in Uttarakhand is evaluated by comparing 17 indicators based on the availability of household amenities and household assets under following heads:

- 1) On the basis of Ownership Status of Households
- 2) On The Basis of Availability of Basic Households Amenities
 - a) Main sources of drinking water
 - b) Availability of drinking water
 - c) Main source of lighting
 - d) Availability of latrine within the premises
 - e) Waste water outlet connected to
 - f) Bathing facilities available within the premises
 - g) Availability of kitchen
 - h) Fuel used for cooking
- 3) On The Basis Of Availability Of Information And Communication Technology
 - a) Percentage of households having radio
 - b) Percentage of households having television
 - c) Percentage of households having computer/laptop
 - d) Percentage of households having mobile phones
- 4) On The Basis Availability Of Transportation Facilities
 - a) Percentage of households having bicycle
 - b) Percentage of households having scooter/motorbike
 - c) Percentage of households having car/jeep
- 5) On The Basis Of Households Availing Banking Services

On the Basis of Ownership Status of Households

Comparing Ownership Status of Households in Uttarakhand for the year 2001 and 2011

Figure-1: Ownership Status of Household

Figure-1 shows the household status of people in Uttarakhand which is studied for the year 2001 and 2011. No significant change is seen in the percentage of people living in their own houses. A slight increase is appearing in the percentage of people living in rented houses in the year 2011. The ownership

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

status of households in Uttarakhand is showing a stagnant growth which indicates that well-being is not improving in Uttarakhand.

Comparing Ownership Status of Households in Rural and Urban Areas of Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-2 shows that in rural areas percentage of households having their own houses decreased from 90.5% to 89.68% between the period of 2001 and 2011 as a lot of people in Uttarakhand are migrating towards urban areas in search of better jobs and opportunities. In urban areas of Uttarakhand percentage of households having owned houses increased which is showing an improvement in life quality of the people living in urban areas of Uttarakhand. Percentage of households living in rented houses increased in rural areas from 5.4% to 6.39% and decreased in urban areas from 30.8% to 26.63% between 2001 and 2011.

Figure-2: Ownership Status of Households in Rural and Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

On the Basis of Availability of Basic Households Amenities

Comparing the Main Source of Drinking Water in Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-3 shows that the main source of drinking water in Uttarakhand is tap water and water from hand pump. In the year 2011 percentage of household using tap water as drinking water is 68.22% and percentage of household using hand pump water is 22.08%. Tap water increased as a source of drinking water by 2.32% between the year 2001 and 2011. Hand pump water usage also increased from the year 2001 to 2011 by 2.22%. The growth shown in percentage of tap water and hand pump water is very less. All other sources contribute very less as the source of drinking water.

Comparing the Main Source of Drinking Water in Rural and Urban Areas of Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-4 represents that the main source of drinking water in rural and urban areas of Uttarakhand is tap water followed by hand pump water. The percentage of rural households using tap water in the year 2011 is 63.92% and the percentage of urban households using tap water in the year 2011 is 78.42%. After tap water, the main source of drinking water used in urban and rural Uttarakhand is hand pump water. The percentage of households using hand pump water is more in rural areas as compared to urban areas i.e percentage of rural household using hand pump water is 24.07% and percentage of urban household using hand pump water is 17.14%. Other sources of water include water from well, tube well, spring and river, etc.

Figure-3: Main Source of Drinking Water

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-4: Main Source of Drinking Water in Rural and Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Comparing the Availability of Drinking Water in Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

- Availability of drinking water is assessed under following three heads:-
- Within the premises: If the source located within the premises where the households lived
- Near the premises: If the source was located within a range of 100 meter from the premises in urban area and within a distance of 500 meters in case of rural areas
- Away from the premises: If the source was located beyond 100 meter from the premises in urban area and beyond 500 meters in rural areas

Figure-5: Availability of Drinking Water

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

The two Census data shows a substantial increase in drinking water availability within the premises in Uttarakhand as it increased from 44.8% to 58.26% in the gap of 10 years. Near the premises availability of drinking water shows a decline from 38.5% to 26.59%. It shows a decline of about 1.55% in the availability of drinking water away from the premises in Uttarakhand. Till 2011, 15.15% of drinking water sources were away from the premise which is not a good sign and should be the area of concern to give better life quality to the people of Uttarakhand.

Comparing the Availability of Drinking Water in Rural and Urban Areas of Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-6 shows that within the premises availability of drinking water is very less in rural areas as compared to urban areas. The growth in the within premises availability of drinking water is very less in rural areas of Uttarakhand from the year 2001 to 2011. In 2011 the percentage of rural households having availability of drinking water within the premises is 45.42% and the percentage of urban households having availability of drinking water within the premises is 88.69%. Till 2011, 20.5% of rural households have drinking water availability away from the premises. This shows the adverse living condition of the rural population of Uttarakhand.

Figure-6: Availability of Drinking Water in Rural and Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Comparing the Main Source of Lighting in Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-7: Main Source of Lighting

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-7 shows that in Uttarakhand state people are highly depending on electricity and kerosene for lighting. Electricity usage increased from the year 2001 to 2011 by 26.74% which is a good sign for Uttarakhand development and the dependence on kerosene for lighting decreased substantially from the year 2001 to 2011 by 26.23 %. Solar contribute very less as the source of lighting i.e. 1.9% in the 2001 and 1.22% in 2011. No lighting in Uttarakhand accounted for 0.32% in 2011.

Comparing the Main Source of Lighting in Rural and Urban Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-8: represents that the main source of lighting in urban and rural Uttarakhand is electricity. In 2001 the rural households were dependent on kerosene for lighting but the situation changed in 2011 as the percentage of rural households using electricity as a main source of lighting increased in 2011 by 33.2% and the percentage of rural households using kerosene as a source of lighting decreased by 32.17%. in urban areas the main source of lighting is electricity and all other sources contribute very less. The percentage of urban households using electricity in 2011 is 96.49%.

Figure-8: Main Source of Lighting in Rural and Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Comparing the Percentage of Households Having Latrine within Premises in Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-9: Latrine within the Premises

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-9 represents the availability of toilets within the premises. The percentage of toilets availability from the year 2001 to 2011 shows an increase of 20.67 % which is a good indicator towards an increase in well-being in Uttarakhand. The percentage of unavailability of latrine within the premises declined from 54.8% to 34.23% between the years 2001 and 2011. Availability of latrine being the issue of hygiene and well-being need much attention as unavailability of latrine till 2011 accounts for 34.23%.

Comparing the Percentage of Households Having Latrine within Premises in Rural and Urban Areas of Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-10: Latrine within the Premises in Rural and Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-10: shows that the percentage of rural households having latrine within the premises increased by 22.46% between the year 2001 and 2011. This figure also shows that in 2011, 45.94% of the rural households does not have latrine within the premises which shows the poor well-being in rural Uttarakhand. The situation in urban Uttarakhand is better as 93.57% of the urban household have latrine within the premises in 2011.

Comparing Drainage Scenario in Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-11: Drainage Scenario

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-11 shows the type of drainage system connectivity in Uttarakhand. The percentage of households having closed drainage connectivity is 19.02% in 2011. The above graph shows the adverse living condition in Uttarakhand as in 2011 the percentage of households having open drainage connectivity accounts for 42.1% and 38.8% of the households does not have drainage connectivity in Uttarakhand.

Comparing the Drainage Scenario in Rural and Urban Areas of Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-12: Drainage Scenario in Rural and Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

percentage of households having closed drainage connectivity is 42.26% in 2011 and the percentage of urban households having open drainage is 50.65% in 2011. The well-being in Uttarakhand is bad in both urban and rural areas.

Figure-12 represents the drainage connectivity in urban and rural areas of Uttarakhand. The percentage of households having no drainage connectivity in rural areas decreased from 65% to 11.8% between the year 2001 and 2011. The poor living condition in rural Uttarakhand is visible by the percentage of households having open drainage connectivity i.e 59.9%. In urban areas of Uttarakhand the

Comparing the Availability of Bathing Facility within the Premises in Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-13: Bathing Facility within the Premises

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-13 shows the bathing facility available within the premises in Uttarakhand. In Uttarakhand availability of bathroom facility within the premises is showing an increase of 30.53% between the period of 2001 and 2011 indicating growth in well-being. As the bathroom facility is increasing in Uttarakhand an obvious decline in the unavailability of bathroom facility can be seen in the above graph in 2001 unavailability of the bathroom is

accounted for 61.2% and in 2011 it declined to 30.67%. The major concern is that till 2011 unavailability of the bathroom is too high i.e. 30.67% which is an indicator of bad life quality in Uttarakhand.

Comparing the Availability of Bathing Facility within the Premises in Rural and Urban Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-14: Bathing Facility within the Premises in Rural and Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-14 shows an increase in within the premises availability of bathing facilities in rural areas as the percentage of rural household having bathroom facilities within the premises increased by 33.31% between 2001 and 2011 but the growth is insufficient as 40.69% of the rural household does not have bathing facility in the premises till 2011. In 2011 the percentage of urban households having bathing facility within the premises is 93.7% which shows that the standard of living is better in urban areas of Uttarakhand.

Comparing the Availability of Kitchen in Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-15: Availability of Kitchen in Percentage

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-15 is showing kitchen availability in Uttarakhand. The kitchen is the main part of all the houses. The graph is showing stagnant growth in availability of kitchen as in 2001 71.3 % of the households have kitchen which decreased 70.14% in the year 2011. The percentage of household not having kitchen accounts for 29.6 % in the year 2011.

Comparing the Availability of Kitchen in Rural and Urban Areas of Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-16: Availability of Kitchen in Rural and Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-16 shows that the percentage of household having separate kitchen are more in urban areas of Uttarakhand. The percentage of households not having kitchen in urban areas account for 15.71% while the percentage of households not having kitchen in rural areas is 35.45% which shows poor well-being in rural areas of Uttarakhand.

Comparing the Fuel used for Cooking in Uttarakhand in the Years 2001 and 2011

Figure-17: Fuel used for Cooking

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-17 represents the percentage of different types of fuel used for cooking in Uttarakhand. In 2001, firewood was the main fuel used for cooking which accounts for 54.2% but it declined in 2011 to 14.02%. In 2011 the main fuel used for cooking was LPG which accounts for 79.42% and it increased by 45.92% between 2001 and 2011. The increase or the shift from firewood to LPG indicates the increase in well-being in Uttarakhand. The scenario for 2011 is that 93.44% of fuel used for cooking in Uttarakhand includes only firewood and LPG and rest 6.56% includes all other fuels used for cooking like kerosene, coal, and cow dung cakes, etc.

Comparing the Fuel used for Cooking in Rural Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-18: Fuel used for Cooking in Rural Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-18 shows that most of the cooking in rural households is done by using firewood as a fuel. The percentage of households using firewood as fuel decreased from the year 2001 to 2011 from 67.5% to 63.29% but still is the main fuel used for cooking in the rural areas of Uttarakhand. LPG is also used as a fuel for cooking. The percentage of households using LPG as fuel for cooking accounts for 29.4% in the year 2011. All other fuels are not commonly used for cooking in rural Uttarakhand.

Comparing the Fuel used for Cooking in Urban Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-19: Fuel used for Cooking in Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-19 represents that the major cooking in urban areas is dependent on LPG. In 2011 the percentage of households using LPG as fuel in urban areas of Uttarakhand is 79.42% while the percentage of households using firewood is 14.02%. This is showing better well-being in urban areas of Uttarakhand.

On the Basis of Information and Communication Technology

Comparing the Percentage of Households Having Radio/Transistor in Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-20 represents the percentage of households having radio or transistor in Uttarakhand. In 2001, 49.7% of the households were having radio or transistor and number households not having radio or transistor were accounted for 50.3%. In 2011 only 14.56% of the households in Uttarakhand were having radio or transistor and 85.44% of the households were not having radio or transistor. The decline in the percentage of households owning the radio or transistor between the period of 2001 and 2011 may not be due to the decline in well-being but due to the new inventions and availability of television and mobile phones.

Figure-20: Percentage of Households Having Radio/Transistor

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

the introduction of new technology. In 2001 only 15.9% of the rural households have radio or transistor. The percentage of urban households having radio or transistor in 2001 is 11.4%.

Comparing the Percentage of Households Having Radio/Transistor in Rural and Urban Areas of Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-21 compares the rural and urban households in Uttarakhand on the basis of availability of radio or transistor for the year 2001 and 2011. The graph shows that there is continuous decrease in the percentage of households owning radio or transistor in both urban and rural areas of Uttarakhand. The reason for the decrease may be

Figure-21: Percentage of Households Having Radio/Transistor in Rural and Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

2011, 38.02% of the households do not have a television.

Comparing the Percentage of Households Having Television in Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-22 shows the percentage of households in Uttarakhand having television. In 2001, 42.98% of households have a television but it increased to 61.98% in 2011. The increase in the percentage of households owning television by 19.08% shows an increase in life quality. Above figure shows that the percentage of households not having television decreased between 2001 and 2011 by 19.08%. The graph also shows that in

Figure-22: Percentage of Households Having Television

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Comparing the Percentage of Households Having Television in Rural and Urban Areas of Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-23 shows that the percentage of rural households having television increased from 32.3% to 53.3% between the year 2001 and 2011. The graph also shows that till 2011 the percentage of households not having television is 46.7% which shows poor well-being in rural areas of Uttarakhand. The percentage of households having television in urban areas in 2001 is 82.55%.

Figure-23: Percentage of Households Having Television in Rural and Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Percentage of Households Having Computer/Laptop in Uttarakhand for the Year 2011

Figure-24 represents the percentage of households having computer/laptop. The graph shows that in the year 2011, 89.07% of the households in Uttarakhand do not have computer or laptop. The inferiority in well-being in Uttarakhand can be evaluated from the fact that only 3.16% of the households have computer or laptop

with the internet connection and 7.77% of households have computer or laptop without internet connection.

Figure-24: Percentage of Households Having Computer/Laptop in 2011

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

The data for computer and laptop availability was not included in 2001 Census (may be the technology was not widely used) so the comparison between 2001 and 2011 could not be done.

Percentage of Households Having Telephone/Mobile Phone in Uttarakhand for the Year 2011

Figure-25 shows that in 2011, 64.8% of the households have mobile phones in Uttarakhand. The percentage of households having both mobile phones and landlines in houses is 6.62%. The graph also

represents that there are many households in Uttarakhand that does not use mobile phones or landlines. The percentage of households not having mobile phones or landlines accounts for 25.41% in Uttarakhand for the year 2011.

Figure-25: Percentage of Households Having Telephone/Mobile in 2011

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

The data for the year 2001 on mobile phones was not available so the comparison was difficult. The data from the 2001 census shows that the percentage of households using telephones is 9.9%. Percentage of rural households using telephones in 2001 was 4.4% and the percentage of urban households using telephones was 26.7%.

On the Basis Availability of Transportation Facilities

Comparing the Percentage of Households Having Bicycle in Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-26: Percentage of Households Having Bicycle

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-26 represents the percentage of households in Uttarakhand which have a bicycle. In the year 2001, the percentage of people having bicycle was 30.9% and increased to 31.29% in 2011. This graph shows a very less increase in the percentage of households having a bicycle. In 2011 the percentage of households not having bicycle was 68.71%.

Comparing the Percentage of Households Having Bicycle in Urban and Rural Areas of Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-27: Percentage of Households Having Bicycle in Rural and Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-27 compares rural and urban percentage of households having bicycle in Uttarakhand for the year 2001 and 2011. In 2011 the percentage of rural households not having bicycle accounts for 72.51% and the percentage of urban households not having bicycle is 59.68%. This shows adverse condition of the people living in Uttarakhand.

Comparing the Percentage of Households Having Scooter/Motorcycle/Moped in Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-28: Percentage of Households Having Scooter/Motorcycle/Moped

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-28 shows the percentage of households having scooter/motorcycle in Uttarakhand. In 2001, only 11.9% of the households have motorbike or scooter in their houses and it increased to 22.88% in 2011. The percentage of people not having scooter or motorbike was 88.1% in 2001 and decreased to 77.12% in 2011.

Comparing the Percentage of Households Having Scooter/Motorcycle/Moped in Rural and Urban areas of Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-29 shows the percentage of households having scooter/motorcycle/moped in rural and urban areas of Uttarakhand. The percentage of rural households having scooter increased from 6.2% to 15.06% between 2001 and 2011 and the percentage of urban households having scooter increased from 29.7% to 41.46% between the year 2001 and 2011. In rural areas the percentage of households not having scooter accounts for 84.94% in the year 2011 which shows unpleasant life quality in rural areas of Uttarakhand. The situation is better in urban areas but still needs a lot of improvement as 58.54 % households does not have scooter in the year 2011.

Figure-29: Percentage of Households Having Scooter/Motorcycle/Moped in Rural and Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Comparing the Percentage of Households Having Car/Jeep/Van in Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-30: Percentage of Household Having Car/Jeep/Van

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-30 represents the percentage of households having car or jeep as their household asset. In 2001 only 2.7% of the people have car or jeep which increased to 6.21% in 2011. This increase in the percentage of households having car/jeep is very less and indicating towards a poor well-being in Uttarakhand. 93.79% of the households in Uttarakhand do not have any kind of car/jeep till the year 2011.

Comparing the Percentage of Households Having Car/Jeep/Van in Rural and Urban Areas of Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-31: Percentage of Households Having Car/Jeep/Van in Rural and Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-31 represents that the percentage of households having car, jeep or van in rural and urban areas of Uttarakhand is very less. No significant growth is visible from the year 2001 to 2011 in the rural and urban percentage of households having car/jeep/van. Till 2011, 96.7% of the rural households do not have any car/jeep/van facilities in the house. The percentage of urban households no having car/jeep/van accounts for 86.18% showing inferior life quality in both rural and urban areas of Uttarakhand.

On the Basis of Households Availing Banking Services

Comparing the Percentage of Households Availing Banking Services in Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-32: Percentage of Households Availing Banking Services

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

households not taking the advantage of banking services accounts for 19.29%.

Figure-32 shows the percentage of households in Uttarakhand availing banking services. An increase is seen in the percentage of households taking advantage of banks and banking services in the year 2011 which shows improvement in the life quality of people living in Uttarakhand. In 2001, 59.8% of the people were availing banking services which increased to 80.71 % in the year 2011. A decrease has come in the percentage of the households not availing banking services. In 2011 the percentage of the

Comparing the Percentage of Households Availing Banking Services in Rural and Urban Areas of Uttarakhand (2001 and 2011)

Figure-33: Percentage of Households Availing Banking Services in Rural and Urban Areas

Source: Census 2001 and Census 2011

Figure-33 shows increase in the percentage of households availing banking services in both rural and urban areas of Uttarakhand from the year 2001 till 2011. In 2011 percentage of urban households availing banking services is 81.8% and percentage of rural households availing banking services is 80.8% which indicates toward good well-being in both rural and urban areas of Uttarakhand.

V. CONCLUSION

Major Findings

- 1) Ownership status of households is showing stagnant growth in well-being in Uttarakhand. The comparison between rural and urban ownership status of households is showing that people are migrating towards urban areas in Uttarakhand as owned houses in the urban areas of Uttarakhand has increased and the percentage of households having their own houses in rural areas of Uttarakhand has decreased. The possible reason of this migration can be poor well-being in Uttarakhand, lack of job opportunities and poor education facilities etc.
- 2) Rural and urban wise availability of household amenities indicates that well-being is better in the urban areas of Uttarakhand as compared to the rural areas
 - Only 45.42% of the households in rural areas have drinking water within the premises.
 - 96.49% of the urban households in Uttarakhand are using electricity as the main source of lighting.
 - Less than 50% of the rural households in Uttarakhand have latrine and bathing facilities within the premises.
 - Main fuel used for cooking by rural households in Uttarakhand is firewood.
- 3) In 2011, 89.07 % of household does not have computer or laptop in Uttarakhand which shows poor performance in IT sector.
- 4) Less than 30% of the people have bicycle or scooter in Uttarakhand and only 6% have car or jeep which shows the problem of transportation for the people living in Uttarakhand.
- 5) Almost 80% of household in both rural and urban areas are availing banking services in Uttarakhand which indicates towards the improvement in well-being of the people living in Uttarakhand.

Recommendations

- 1) Government should focus on the problem of the people living in rural region of Uttarakhand such as non-availability of drinking water and household amenities like latrine and bathing facilities within or near the premises.
- 2) Government should take initiatives to provide good transportation facilities to the people in Uttarakhand.
- 3) Policies should be made to encourage the use of LPG cylinders and smokeless chullhas in rural areas of Uttarakhand.
- 4) Information and communication sector development in Uttarakhand should be the main focus of the Government.

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